

COMPARTMENT SYNDROME FOLLOWING A SNAKE BITE

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Keywords

Compartment syndrome,

Snake bite,

Fasciotomy,

Antivenom

ABSTRACT

Compartment syndrome is a potentially life-threatening condition that can occur following trauma, such as a snake bite. It results from increased pressure within a muscle compartment, leading to decreased blood flow, tissue damage, and potential loss of limb function. Early recognition and intervention are essential to prevent irreversible damage.

INTRODUCTION

Depending on the content of the venom after a snake bite, various clinical findings ranging from local findings to death may be observed. The most common findings due to snake bites are fang marks, edema and ecchymosis. Acute compartment syndrome is a condition that can cause permanent disorders if not diagnosed and treated in a timely manner, and can lead to limb loss in patients with inadequate treatment. It is reported in the literature as 1.36%-16.6%.¹ It is most commonly seen in the volar forearm in the upper extremity and in the anterior and deep posterior compartments in the lower extremity.

CASE

A 16-year-old male patient presented to the emergency department after being bitten by a snake on the second finger of his left hand while working in the garden. The patient had already received one dose of antivenom.

Upon evaluation, the patient was alert, oriented, and cooperative. His main complaints included severe pain, tenderness, and limited mobility in his left arm. Physical examination revealed swelling, ecchymosis, and an increase in temperature in the left forearm. The range of motion in the left wrist and elbow was painful and restricted. During clinical examination, the 5 Ps of compartment syndrome were present: pain, pallor, paresthesia, paralysis, pulselessness. His blood findings were normal. Given the clinical findings and worsening symptoms, the orthopedics team diagnosed compartment syndrome. The patient was promptly taken to surgery for fasciotomy to relieve the pressure. After a successful operation, the patient showed improvement and was discharged in stable condition following a few days of postoperative monitoring (Figure 1.a,b,c).

FIGURE 1.

a. Fasciotomy of left dorsum hand b. Fasciotomy of left forearm c. Last image before being discharged from the hospital

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16733420

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DISCUSSION

Compartment syndrome is a rare but severe complication of snake bites, resulting from increased pressure within a muscle compartment.¹ In this case, the patient's rapid deterioration with the classic 5 Ps (pain, pallor, paresthesia, paralysis, pulselessness) prompted immediate diagnosis and treatment.^{1,2} The presence of these symptoms highlights the importance of early recognition and intervention in preventing irreversible damage such as nerve injury, muscle necrosis, or even loss of limb function. Snake venom can cause significant local inflammation, leading to edema and increased compartment pressure. Although antivenom administration is essential in neutralizing the systemic effects of snake venom, as seen here, it may not prevent local complications like compartment syndrome.^{2,3} The patient in this case received antivenom prior to developing compartment syndrome, emphasizing the need for vigilance in monitoring for this condition even after appropriate venom treatment.

The definitive treatment for compartment syndrome is fasciotomy, which effectively relieves the elevated pressure. It is important that the compartment pressure measured for diagnostic purposes is above 10 mmHg. If the diagnosis is not made in time, necrosis, fibrosis and contracture of the extremity may develop. In treatment, immobilization of the bitten area, elevation, anti-edema and antivenom are recommended.^{1,3} If the compartment pressure, which is normally 10 mmHg, is above 30 mmHg, there are those who recommend early fasciotomy, while there are also studies indicating that muscle necrosis is seen at a high rate in those who undergo fasciotomy and that it is rarely performed.⁴⁻⁸ In this case, the timely surgical intervention resulted in a positive outcome, with the patient recovering well. The prompt response from the emergency and orthopedic teams was key in preventing long-term damage.

This case underscores the importance of maintaining a high index of suspicion for compartment syndrome following snake bites. Despite appropriate antivenom treatment, continuous monitoring and early surgical consultation are essential to ensure the best possible patient outcomes.

CONCLUSION

This case highlights the potential for rapid deterioration following a snake bite, emphasizing the importance of prompt diagnosis and treatment of compartment syndrome. Surgical

intervention, such as fasciotomy, is essential to prevent permanent damage and ensure full recovery.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

Acknowledgements

No

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